

Effect of Myofascial Induction Therapy in Patients of Oral Submucous Fibrosis on Maximal Interincisal Distance Among Young Adult Tobacco Chewers: An Experimental Study

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Abstract

Background: Oral Submucous Fibrosis (OSMF) is a chronic, potentially malignant condition that is common in South Asia and is characterized by progressive submucosal fibrosis and very limited mouth opening. What is yet to be explored in this population is the use of Myofascial Induction therapy (MIT), a manual physiotherapy technique aimed at fascial systems

Methods: An experimental pre-post study was done on 30 males (20–39 years old) with Stage A or B OSMF and >3-year history of tobacco use. They undertook three sessions of transverse sliding MIT in one week. The Maximal Interincisal Distance (MID) was assessed at baseline and after each session using a manual Vernier caliper.

Results: The mean MID improved significantly from a baseline of 24.4 ± 4.55 mm to 28.3 ± 4.40 mm ($p < 0.0013$). The gains were always consistent across sessions, with Stage B participants having a higher mean improvement (4.67mm) compared to those with Stage A (3.71mm), where more fibrotic bands were treated.

Conclusion: Myofascial Induction Therapy is an effective non-invasive intervention for increased mouth opening in early-to-moderate OSMF. The results point to the fact that mechanotransduction of the fascial system facilitates extracellular matrix reorganization and improves functional mobility.

Introduction

Oral Submucous Fibrosis (OSMF) is insidious, chronic disease characterized by juxta-epithelial inflammatory reaction and the progress of fibroelastic changes in the lamina propria of the oral cavity and sometimes the pharynx as well. In this condition, trismus and functional impairment in mouth-opening is caused by the pathognomonic rigidity of the oral mucosa^[1].

The global prevalence of OSMF is South and Southeast Asia primarily due to ethnic cultural dietary habits involving areca nut and smokeless tobacco consumption. Prevalence in the Indian subcontinent is recorded at from 0.62% to 6.42%, though with a demographic shift toward the youth, particularly males, largely accredited to the popularized consumption of the ready-made tobacco preparations, gutkha and kharra^[2].

The biochemical pathogenesis of OSMF is predicated on the alkaloids and tannins found in areca nuts. Arecoline is the dominant alkaloid and is responsible for fibroblast proliferation and synthesis of collagen, whereas tannins are responsible for decreased collagen degradation by inhibiting collagenase activity. This results in an overgrowth of collagen fibers and loss of tissue elasticity^[3].

The therapeutic options available presently, despite the observed potential of malignant transformation into oral squamous cell carcinoma, provide a cocktail of intralesional steroid-injection with alternative treatments that produce uncertain efficacy results in the long term, coupled with massive surgical-relapse rates in the majority of surgical treatment options such as fibrotomy^[4].

Physiotherapy is an important conservative measure, but a recent 2025 meta-analysis shows that stretching exercises yield a mean improvement of 1.19mm in mouth opening. Manual therapy protocols that deal with the actual fascial restrictions and not the mucosal bands need to be devised^[5].

Myofascial Induction Therapy (MIT) is “a newly defined manual medicine paradigm involving functional re-induction of the fascial matrix utilizing gentle mechanical induction and mechanotransduction. Though the MIT has efficacy in the treatment of radiation-induced trismus among cancer survivors, MIT’s use on areca nut-induced OSMF is hardly explored^[6].

This study, thus, aims to fill the gap for conservative management of this debilitating condition by evaluating the effect of the specific transverse sliding MIT protocol on the Maximal Interincisal Distance (MID) of young adult tobacco chewers.

Methods

Study Design and Ethical Considerations

The study was performed using a pre-post interventional experimental design over 12 months at the physiotherapy department of a tertiary medical center. Ethical clearance was received from the Institutional Ethics Committee (IRB/Ethics Approval-366-2024/03).

The study followed the ethics of the Helsinki declaration to the letter. Before signing written informed consent, all participants were given detailed information about the study’s objectives and procedures in their native language (Marathi, Hindi, or English).

Participation was entirely voluntary, and subjects were informed of their right to opt out of the experiment at any stage of the trial without compromising their medical treatment going forward.

Participant Selection and Characteristics

Using a convenient sampling technique, a total of 30 male participants were recruited. The youths were targeted for selection because this group is mostly affected by the aggressive use of

the smokeless tobacco products in central India.

Criteria	Requirements for Inclusion/Exclusion
Inclusion Criteria	Males aged 20-39 years with a history of tobacco/kharra use >6 times/day for >3 years.
	Clinically diagnosed OSMF Stage A (MID >20mm) or Stage B (MID 11-19mm).
	Presence of palpable fibrous bands and healthy anterior dentition.
Exclusion Criteria	History of oral malignancy, recent dental or TMJ surgery, or presence of "red flags" (fever, unexplained weight loss) ^[7] .
	Concurrent consumption of alcohol or cigarette smoking.
	Profound trismus (MID <10mm) or presence of acute TMJ inflammation/infection.

The choice of the 20-39 age group comes from epidemiological data showing that OSF occurs frequently among younger men in central India. This is mostly due to the popularity of kharra and gutkha.

Instrumentation and Outcome Measurement

The main outcome measure was the Maximal Interincisal Distance (MID). This is the widest separation between the upper and lower central incisors when the mouth is opened as wide as possible. We used a manual Vernier caliper for its precision of 0.02 mm and its reliability in clinical settings^[8].

To ensure accurate measurements and reduce parallax error, participants sat upright on a stool with their heads in a neutral position against a wall. The therapist positioned themselves directly in front of the patient at eye level with the caliper. Each measurement was taken three times, and the average value was recorded to ensure high reliability with the examiner. This procedure was followed at baseline, before the intervention, and right after completing each of the three MIT sessions^[9].

Myofascial Induction Therapy Protocol

The intervention used the "transverse sliding method" of Myofascial Induction Therapy, as described by Pilat.

Preparation: The participant lay on their back with their neck in a neutral position. The therapist sat at the head of the table.

Palpation: The therapist felt for the intraoral fibrotic bands by placing their thumb inside the mouth against the buccal mucosa while the other four fingers applied external counterpressure.

Induction Technique: Once a band was located, the therapist applied a gentle, sustained downward pressure with the thumb tip. While keeping this pressure, a transverse stroke was performed at a right angle to the fibrotic band.

Dosage and Duration: The intervention included three sets of 15 cycles for each identified band. A cycle was one complete back-and-forth movement, done at a rhythm of about one cycle per

second.

Session Frequency: The treatment program included three sessions held on alternate days over a week. Each session lasted from 8 to 20 minutes, depending on how many bands were present.

This "induction" approach is different from traditional passive stretching because it focuses on facilitating tissue movement rather than forcing it. The goal is to trigger metabolic and biochemical responses through mechanotransduction^[10].

Statistical Analysis

We used SPSS version 21.0 for statistical analysis. We assessed data normality with the Shapiro-Wilk test, along with histograms and Q-Q plots. We calculated descriptive statistics, including means and standard deviations, for all demographic variables and MID values. We conducted paired t-tests for intragroup comparisons between pre-intervention and post-intervention scores across the three sessions. Confidence intervals were set at 95%, and a p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Demographic and Addiction Profiles

The study included 30 male participants with a mean age of 30.4 years . The age distribution showed that 80% of the participants were between the ages of 26 and 35, highlighting the vulnerability of this specific workforce demographic to tobacco-related oral morbidity.

Age Group (Years)	Number of Subjects (%)
20-25	4 (13.33%)
26-30	12 (40.00%)
31-35	12 (40.00%)
36-39	2 (6.67%)

Addiction analysis revealed that 56.67% of subjects primarily used gutkha, while 43.33 % preferred kharra. In terms of clinical severity, 80% of participants were classified as Stage A (MID >20mm), and 20% were classified as Stage B (MID 11–19 mm).

Primary Outcome: Overall Improvement in MID

Normality testing via the Shapiro-Wilk test confirmed that both pre-intervention data ($W = 0.9693$, $p = 0.5213$) and post-intervention data ($W = 0.948$, $p = 0.150$) were normally distributed, justifying the use of parametric tests.

The cumulative effect of three MIT sessions resulted in an extremely significant improvement in mouth opening. The mean MID increased from 24.4 ± 4.55 mm at baseline to 28.3 ± 4.40 mm at the end of the one-week protocol. This represents a total mean gain of 3.9 mm ($p < 0.001332$).

Session-Wise Analysis

Analysis of individual sessions demonstrated that MIT provided consistent, incremental gains in every treatment encounter.

Session Number	Pre-MID (Mean ± SD)	Post-MID (Mean ± SD)	Mean Gain	p-value
First Session	24.4 ± 4.55 mm	26.8 ± 4.66 mm	2.4 mm	0.0480
Second Session	25.33 ± 4.57mm	27.83 ± 4.54 mm	2.5 mm	0.0379
Third Session	25.97 ± 4.48mm	28.3 ± 4.40 mm	2.37 mm	0.0464

The data indicates that the most substantial single-session gain occurred during the second session (2.5 mm), while the total improvement was statistically significant at each stage of the intervention.

Staging Comparison: Stage A vs. Stage B

A critical finding of this study was the differential response between participants with varying disease severity. While both groups showed extremely significant improvements overall, the magnitude of the change differed significantly.

OSMF Stage	Pre-Protocol MID (Mean ± SD)	Post-Protocol MID (Mean ± SD)	Final Gain	p-value
Stage A (n=24)	26.08 ± 3.30 mm	29.79 ± 3.46 mm	3.71 mm	0.0004
Stage B (n=6)	17.67 ± 1.51 mm	22.33 ± 1.97 mm	4.67 mm	0.0011

Stage B participants, despite having more advanced fibrosis, achieved a higher total mean gain (4.67 mm) than Stage A participants (3.71 mm). This observation suggests that the greater number of fibrotic bands in Stage B subjects allowed for a larger volume of "induction" therapy to be applied per session, as each band was treated as a separate site for the transverse sliding protocol.

Discussion

The results of this experimental study show that Myofascial Induction Therapy (MIT) is an effective manual treatment for increasing Maximal Interincisal Distance (MID) in young adults with early to moderate Oral Submucous Fibrosis (OSMF). In just one week and after three treatment sessions, participants experienced an average MID increase of 3.9 mm. This result is important compared to current physiotherapy standards in managing OSMF.

Mechanotransduction and Physiological Mechanisms

The improvements observed in this study are based on mechanotransduction within the fascial system. OSMF involves a buildup of collagen fibers and dense cross-links that limit the normal movement of the submucosal fascial planes. Myofascial Induction Therapy uses mechanical forces like transverse sliding and friction to activate mechanoreceptors in the fascia.

Applying these mechanical loads triggers a cellular response in the fibroblasts. This helps reorganize the extracellular matrix (ECM) and improves the arrangement of collagen fibers. The mechanotransduction response restores the slip properties between tissue layers, effectively

"loosening" the stiff surface of the oral mucosa. Moreover, manual induction has been shown to improve local micro-circulation and lymphatic drainage, potentially relieving the lack of blood flow typically found in fibrotic tissues and supporting a healthier tissue environment. Unlike intense passive stretching, which can cause micro-trauma and reactive fibrosis, MIT aims to "facilitate" movement. This engages the central nervous system's regulatory mechanisms to achieve lasting tissue relaxation^[11].

Comparison with Recent Literature

The effectiveness of MIT observed in this study, with a 3.9 mm gain in one week, is favorable when compared to recent literature. A 2025 meta-analysis by Bodhade et al. reviewed 20 studies on physiotherapy for OSMF. It found that standard physiotherapy alone—mainly consisting of active and passive stretching—yielded a modest average increase of only 1.19 mm over a longer period of 2 to 6 weeks. Even when physiotherapy was combined with medication like steroids or hyaluronidase, improvements often took months, not days^[5].

Recent clinical trials have also looked into MIT for other orofacial issues. Ortiz-Comino et al. (2022) showed that a 6-week MIT program notably improved mouth opening and temporomandibular dysfunction in head and neck cancer survivors. Our findings extend this evidence to those with areca nut-induced fibrosis, indicating that the bands caused by areca nut may respond better to rapid manual induction than the fibrosis seen in cancer patients. Another study by Castro-Martín et al. (2021) noted the immediate effects of a single MIT session on neck and shoulder movement in cancer survivors, emphasizing the quick physiological response of fascial tissue to induction methods^[12].

Interestingly, participants at Stage B showed greater gains (4.67 mm) compared to Stage A (3.71 mm). This difference may be due to the density of the intervention. Stage B participants often had multiple faucial and buccal bands requiring more treatment sites. Since the therapist works on each palpable band separately, Stage B participants received a higher total therapeutic "dosage." This suggests that MIT may be particularly helpful for patients in the moderate stages of the disease, where the amount of fibrotic tissue is considerable but not yet irreversible.

Clinical Implications for Physiotherapy Practice

This research strongly supports including MIT in standard conservative management for OSMF. For musculoskeletal physiotherapists, this technique offers a non-invasive, cost-effective manual method that does not rely on expensive treatments like ultrasound or laser therapy. The "transverse sliding" technique is relatively easy to learn and apply, making it suitable for clinical practice in rural or resource-limited settings where OSMF is common.

Additionally, the quick results achieved within one week are critical for keeping patients engaged. Patient compliance often poses a challenge in OSMF treatment, as traditional stretching programs can be painful and slow to show progress. Demonstrating a 2.4 mm improvement after the first session can provide a significant psychological boost, encouraging patients to continue

both clinical treatment and their home exercise routines.

Limitations and Future Directions

Despite the significant findings, this study has limitations. The sample size was limited to 30 males, which may not reflect the response in female patients or those at advanced disease stages (Stage C). Moreover, the lack of long-term follow-up means we cannot confirm the sustainability of these gains. Future research should utilize a randomized controlled trial (RCT) design with a sham intervention or traditional exercise control group to isolate the specific effects of MIT. Studies should also investigate MIT's impact on patient-reported outcomes, such as the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) for burning sensation and the WHOQOL-BREF for quality of life, to see if the physical improvements in mouth opening lead to better overall well-being.

Conclusion

Myofascial Induction Therapy, using the transverse sliding method, is an effective and fast intervention for improving mouth opening in young adult males with Oral Submucous Fibrosis. The study found a statistically significant average improvement of 3.9 mm in Maximal Interincisal Distance over just three sessions, with particularly strong results in Stage B patients. These findings suggest that targeting the fascial system through mechanotransduction helps reorganize fibrotic tissue more effectively than traditional stretching alone. MIT should be viewed as a vital part of conservative treatment for OSMF, offering a non-invasive way to restore function and enhance the quality of life for patients facing this chronic condition.

Declarations

Ethical Approval: The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee (IRB/Ethics Approval-366-2024/03) and was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

Informed Consent: Written informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

Competing Interests: The authors declare that they have no competing financial or personal interests that could have influenced the research reported in this manuscript.

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